

APULIA PILOT

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Agenda

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Introduction

The Apulian pilot aims to increase the region's attractiveness by assisting policymakers with identifying policies and actions favourable to the region's development and supporting the digitalization of existing and new farms in rural areas.

The idea is to stimulate innovation and the knowledge base in rural areas, reinforcing the links with research and innovation and encouraging learning and professional training in digitalization. It would make it possible to promote the agricultural sector's competitiveness, also favouring generational turnover. This objective wants to encourage agricultural choices to sustainable management of natural resources, therefore processes with high energy efficiency and reduced emissions in the Apulia region. At the same time, the Apulia pilot wants to support regional and local policymakers through proactive advice and technical assistance, stimulating participatory decision-making processes.

Lessons learned

Challenges

- Assist policymakers;
- Promote the digitization of the agricultural sector in the rural areas of Apulia;
- increase environmental and economic sustainability.

Recommendations:

- Continue the dialogue with the stakeholders and try to involve more policymakers as we can;
- Dissemination

Main results achieved

The work done by the Apulian pilot has undoubtedly positively impacted research and collaboration with the Apulia stakeholders. The foresight so far has allowed us both to understand the needs of the Apulia and how could try to meet them. It means:

- increased cooperation among involved stakeholders
- increased insights by building alternative visions and scenarios, complementing information needs and reducing uncertainties
- promoted learning and gaining skills at the individual, organization, and community (regional) levels
- Partial influence on policymakers
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Action Plan alignment and adoption (1)

Alignment with LTV4RA:

- ***stronger***, where farmers and all those who interact with them actively participate in policy and decision-making processes;
- ***connected***, given that digital infrastructures are essential in allowing rural areas to operate and make a large part of the digital transition from an agricultural point of view;
- ***resilient***, from a social and agricultural economic development point of view, where digitization policies create synergies between research, business investment, support for families, education and training and regulatory compliance. At the same time, resilience is also referring to encouraging agricultural choices to sustainable management of natural resources, therefore processes with high energy efficiency and reduced emissions in the Apulia region;
- ***prosperous***, as agricultural digitization can positively affect employment, it would become necessary to hire specialized personnel and improve the added value of agriculture in agri-food activities, for example, through advertising campaigns

Action Plan alignment and adoption (2)

The digitalization of the agricultural sector

- 1 Develop a network with high educational organisations (universities, centres of research, etc.), high companies and farms to help the technological knowledge transfer by providing classes, training, and coaching.
- 2 Build up synergetic critical skills and provide entrepreneurial support and business models, identify training needs to develop skills, develop management skills, develop open-access Business Models, establish the help desk service, and help manage the project outputs.
- 3 Refine the ICT infrastructures in general and improve skills and instruments in favour of existing and new farms in rural areas by helping the policymakers find European and national funds.

Assistance to policymakers

- 1 Create a Strategic Plan up to 2030 with the Apulia policymakers and local municipalities to in carrying out research, study and training activities relating to the newest European and national policies.
- 2 Involve stakeholders with expressions of interest at the local and regional level in the Strategic Plan.
- 3 Approval of the Strategic Plan with the Apulia policymakers and local municipalities.

Apulia case study

The initial goal of the Apulian pilot was to increase the region's attractiveness by identifying policies and actions favourable to the development of existing farms and encouraging the creation of new farms in rural areas.

The action on the production system concerned the promotion of the introduction of new products and services related to the circular and digital economy that encourage new employment, especially for the younger population groups.

From an in-depth analysis, we realized that to get it, it was necessary to solve a not indifferent problem, namely the difficulty of the local policymakers of the definition of appropriate lines operating more performing to implement EU and national strategic planning. So, some aspects will be changed, in-depth, translated and disseminated.

Technical tools

We intend to continue using all technical tools, such as SDM, and text mining, in collaboration with the stakeholders. The main goal is to improve our skills about, in the training part of our staff in these. For these reasons, we think that these tools could be improved. Referring to SDM, for example:

Feedback	Recommendations
<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Lack of Apulia data➤ Appreciated the free access to the SD➤ Initial difficulties overcome➤ Long-term training➤ Beneficial in planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Dissemination➤ Simple instructions➤ Continue to invest in improving SDT

Foresight tools

We also intend to continue using the foresight tools in collaboration with the stakeholders.

- Guide to Deep Dives: Covid
- Guide to Deep Dives: CAP Reform
- Guide to Deep Dives: Green Deal
- The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change
- Inventory of Policy Options (sources of finance)
- ...

Thanks for your attention